

Stickers for your snowboard are cool. Even cooler are the free stickers that come in the mail. Stickers are a must-have, but not everyone wants to spend money on them. How can you get stickers free of charge for your snowboard? This is possible with several simple and easy methods.

The simplest way is for someone to just hand you a sticker. This isn't going to happen unless you are walking around a snowboard event like the US Open or the X-Games. Vendors at these events are hungry for people to take their stickers so they give them to anyone who asks or is walking by their booth.

The other option is to get lucky when you buy a product. Often when you buy snowboard equipment, the company, if they are smart, will send a few stickers with the order. However, this is not always possible. Some products aren't available online so they won't ship them to you so you don't get the stickers that you want. You can think of energy drinks such as Monster or Rock Star. Their stickers are some of the best and I have never been offered a free sticker when I bought a Monster energy drink at my local Quickie Mart.

Another option is to ask for stickers at a Zumiez-certified retailer. They usually have a ton just sitting around taking up space so they might as well be on your board.

The problem remains however. How can I get free stickers in the mail?

Contacting companies directly is the easiest and most efficient way to get in touch with them. It is totally free and can even be done while you sit on your couch and watch Robot Chicken reruns too. You can either call them up, send a letter, fill out the contact form on their website or email them directly. There are many companies you can contact. This requires that you search for email addresses and go through the site content to find contact information or snail mail info. It is best to search for a forum or website that already has this information. Then you just pick and choose which company to contact for your free stickers.

This is not a perfect system because not all companies will send you the stickers for free but a lot of them will.

Vinyl Stickers They will ask you to send them a stamped, self-addressed envelope so they don't have pay postage. The stickers will then be sent to you. Others actually want you to send cash; usually a dollar or two. In those cases you can decide how much time and effort you really want to spend on getting your free stickers but a few free stickers in the mail with very little effort is worth it.